

12th WORLD UNIVERSITIES WRESTLING CHAMPIONSHIP FREE STYLE COMPETITION TECHNICAL ANALYSIS

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Abstract:

The purpose of this study was to make 12th World Universities Wrestling Championships Free style competition technical analysis. There were 85 participants from 19 countries participated in Çorum. The observation form prepared before the competitions with recorded by two researchers, technical analysis of the recordings were obtained. During the competitions, the scores obtained, warnings, winning types, successful techniques recorded in the technical analyze form. In statistical analysis, the percentage distributions for each parameter and match percentage rates were calculated. Statistical was performed by One Way ANOVA and LSD analysis of variance in group comparisons. The number of technical points taken for all weight groups in wrestling competitions were 789 points. The highest number of points was achieved in middleweight groups with 352 and with the maximum number of matches was made with 33 in the middleweight group. In the free style wrestling, ratio for one competition (ROC) was of received number of 10.38 points. Ratio of received points for one competition between weight groups found differences ($p<0.05$). The points of Middleweight group are higher from Lightweight and Heavyweight groups. Lightweight wrestlers 51.85% won by score and while 48.15% won by technical superiority. Middleweight wrestlers 48.48% won by score and while 51.52% won by technical superiority. Heavyweight wrestlers 75% won by score and while 25% won by technical superiority. Iran, Russia and Turkey participated in all category competitions. To get degrees, countries must matches at all sizes. Number of touch in Heavyweight

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wrestlers was more than from lightweight and middleweight wrestlers. Coaches in Countries must follow the wrestlers of competing countries. If necessary, it should go to the weight category setting. Some wrestlers recommended wrestled at the top category or bottom category.

Keywords: world universities wrestling, free style, competition analysis

1. Introduction

Martial arts have complex skills. Wrestling is an important one of martial arts. Accomplishment in wrestling can be by transformation some criterions to high performance that are physical and physiological power, technical ability, mentality tactics, experience and motivation. Ability is so important and success is formed by combining ability with mentality and force. Education at least 5 year, training, national experience and experience in international tournaments for 3 years were necessary to be successful in international area. Best wrestling characteristics can be defined by the technical and tactical analysis of the successful wrestlers in the Olympics, World and European Championships. The countries have to protect and pay attention to the wrestlers that have these characteristics. If trainers know the effective techniques and systems, they can train their wrestlers better. Besides the physical and anthropometric characteristics, number and ratio of applied techniques in the competitions are important too (Atan and İmamoğlu, 2005; Kolukısa et al.2004-a; İmamoğlu et al., 2004; Kolukısa et al., 2004-b; Mayda et al., 2016).

Analyzing the tendency of the development of wrestling in recent years, most of experts agree that for the development of wrestling, including as the element of the program of the Olympic Games, it is necessary to make effort for the increase in effectiveness of wrestling duels at preservation of high intensity of fight throughout the whole fight (Sandberg et al., 2007; Vardar et al., 2007). Ortega et al., (2006), they have explained that they have contributed to the development and acquisition of information to improve the technical analysis of the competition. There are many indicators available for statistical analysis of sport performance. The estimates made inform the changes of the performances of the coaches and the sportsmen. Match or competition analysis is important factor for athletes and trainers (İmamoğlu et al., 2015; Bostancı et al., 2017; Ölçücü et al., 2012).

Mirvic et al. (2011) reported that after the events, feedback provided effective results in the use of positive transformations to improve performance of athletes. Mirvic et al. (2011) explained that this information gathered after the competition is open to

discussing objectively, validly and consistently, and developing new possibilities by analyzing and evaluating the basic items of coaches and athletes. The analysis of competition functions has become an urgent situation in modern developed wrestling. Furthermore, the maintenance of individual problems in training has always been an important study direction for researchers (Tropin, 2013; Ryan and Sampson, 2006). After the preparation period, sports events are a very important test area for athletes and coaches. Because; end of the any training process the achievements are evaluated according to the results of the sport competition (Mizerski, 1972). With every passing year, the competition for prize places is becoming more acute at international competitions on Greco-Roman wrestling. It is connected with constantly growing competitiveness on the base of science and technical achievements' introduction into training process and with perfection of sportsmen's training methodic (Malkov. 2006; Hughes and Bartlett, 2002). It has been argued that some of the rule changes made to make wrestling more active may or may not bring benefits to the wrestling sport. Changes made on the style are not welcomed by wrestlers. In this study, it seems that the result of the rule changes made the differentiation of the score techniques. It is connected with constantly increasing competition on the basis of introduction of achievements of science and technique in the training process and improvement of technique of training of sportsmen (Shatskikh, 2013; Bromber et al., 2014; Iermakov et al., 2016; Tropin et al., 2016).

The main objective of the present study was made an analysis of Freestyle wrestling technique during a 2016 year 12th World Universities Wrestling Championship.

2. Material Method

The 12th World Universities wrestling competitions were held in Çorum / Turkey on 25-30 October 2016 with 85 participants from 19 countries at Hitit University. The competition technical analysis study covers a total of 85 competitions made in 8 weight groups. The 76 matches were recorded by 2 researchers with the pre-prepared observation form and technical analyzes were obtained from the recordings made. The types of winning matches, points earned techniques, techniques made on the ground and in the stands; objections and received warnings were recorded in the developed technical analysis form. World universities Free style competitions were made in 3 minutes of 2 periods.

The statistical analyzes of the percentile distribution for each parameter and the percentages per game were calculated. Statistical analysis of the data was performed

using the SPSS 21.0 program. Statistical was performed by One Way ANOVA and LSD correction test. Significance level was taken as 0.05.

3. Results

In Table 1, the weights are listed in groups as light, medium and heavyweight.

Table 1: Distribution of kilo groups

Kilograms	Groups
57 KG. 61 KG. 65 KG	Lightweight
70 KG. 74 KG. 86 KG	Middleweight
97 KG. 125 KG	Heavyweight

In the competitions, kilograms were grouped and distributed as 57 kg and 65 kg light weight. Seventy kg, 74 kg and 88 kg medium weight, 97 kg and 125 kg weight as heavy weight.

Table 2: Distribution of technical and match numbers scored by each weight groups

Weight Groups	Number of points scored	Number of matches by groups	Ratio of received points for one competition
Lightweight (1)	277	27 Match	10.26
Middleweight (2)	352	33 Match	10.67
Heavyweight (3)	160	16 Match	10.00
Total	789	76 Match	10.38
F/LSD		4,39* , 2>3	

In the free style wrestling, ratio for one competition (ROC) was of received number of 10.38 points. There was a no significant difference between the technical and score points according to weight groups. Number of technical for one competition between Weight Groups found differences ($p<0.05$). Ratio of received points for one competition between Weight Groups found differences ($p<0.05$). The points of Middleweight group are higher from Lightweight and Heavyweight groups (Table 2).

Figure 1: The percentage distribution of weight Groups wrestlers' winning type

In Figure 1 Lightweight wrestlers, 51.85% won by score and while 48.15% won by technical superiority. Middleweight wrestlers 48.48% won by score and while 51.52% won by technical superiority. Heavyweight wrestlers 75% won by score and while 25% won by technical superiority. Number of touch in Heavyweight wrestlers was more than from lightweight and middleweight wrestlers. Coaches in Countries must follow the wrestlers of competing countries. If necessary, it should go to the weight category setting. Some wrestlers recommended wrestled at the top category or bottom category.

Table 3: Number of the points in weight and category groups

Weight Groups	Weight category	n	1/8	1/4	final	Rep.	Total point	Number of matches	Ratio of received points for one competition
Lightweight	57 KG	9	43	24	11	31	109	10	10.90
	61 KG	7	25	12	11	19	67	8	8.38
	65 KG	10	38	26	16	21	101	9	11.22
	Total	26	106	62	38	71	277	27	10.26
Middleweight	70 KG	14	34	34	8	34	110	11	10.00
	74 KG	16	59	11	10	36	116	11	10.55
	86 KG	14	31	31	8	56	126	11	11.45
	Total	44	124	76	26	126	352	33	10.67
Heavyweight	97 KG	8	42	24	20	16	102	9	11.33
	125 KG	7	27	15	5	11	58	7	8.29
	Total	85	69	39	25	27	160	16	10.00

The number of wrestler' category in the middle is higher than the number of wrestlers in the light category and heavy category. The number of Wrestlers should be increased in lightweight and heavyweight on tournaments.

Table 4: Way of finishing matches

Weight Groups	Weight category	Touch	Technique superiority	Touch %	Technique superiority %
Lightweight	57 KG	5	5	50.00	50.00
	61 KG	5	3	62.50	37.50
	65 KG	4	5	44.44	55.56
	Total	14	13	51.85	48.15
Middleweight	70 KG	5	6	45.45	54.55
	74 KG	9	2	81.82	18.18
	86 KG	2	9	18.18	81.82
	Total	16	17	48.48	51.52
Heavyweight	97 KG	9	0	100.00	0.00
	125 KG	3	4	42.86	57.14
	Total	12	4	75.00	25.00

Winning style of Matches in Lightweight category, 57 kg wrestlers was found by score and technical superiority same (50%, 50%). 57 kg and 61 kg wrestlers were found by score and technical superiority different. Winning style of Matches in Middleweight category, 70 kg, 74 kg, and 86 kg wrestlers were found by score and technical superiority different. Winning style of Matches in Heavyweight category, 96 kg wrestlers were found with Touch (100%) and not Technique superiority (0%). Winning style of 125 kg wrestlers were found Touch and Technique superiority similar (Table 4).

Table 5: International Senior 12th World Universities Wrestling Championship
 Free Style Ranking

Rank	Equipe	57 kg	61kg	65 kg	70 kg	74 kg	86 kg	97 kg	125 kg	Total
1	IRI	10	8	8	8	10	10	10	10	74
2	RUS	3	10	8	10	8	6	9	6	60
3	TUR	9	4	4	6	8	6	8	9	54
4	KAZ	6	9	10	6	6	8	-	-	45
5	MDA	4	6	9	-	-	2	6	8	35
6	UKR	-	6	-	9	-	8	-	8	31
7	HUN	-	-	6	-	1	9	4	4	24
8	KGZ	8	-	6	8	-	-	-	-	22
9	POL	2	-	2	1	9	-	6	-	20
10	CAN	8	-	1	-	-	3	3	5	20
11	BLR	-	-	3	4	3	-	8	-	18
12	GER	6	-	-	-	6	-	-	-	12
13	MGL	-	8	-	-	-	-	-	-	8
14	FIN	-	-	-	3	2	-	-	-	5
15	SVK	-	-	-	-	-	4	-	-	4
16	URU	-	-	-	-	4	-	-	-	4

17	ESP	-	-	-	2	1	-	-	3
18	GEO	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	0
18	LAT	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	0

Iran, Russia and Turkey have participated in all category competitions. To get degrees, countries must matches at all sizes.

Table 6: The exposed and given Points of the National Turkish Free-Style Wrestling Team

Weight Categories	Competitions	Exposed Techniques	Given Points	Ratio for one competition in Exposed Techniques	Ratio for one competition in Given Points	Rank
57	3	20	18	6.67	6.00	2
61	1	6	7	6.00	7.00	7
65	2	18	19	9.00	9.50	7
70	3	16	28	5.33	9.33	5
74	3	21*	13	7.00	4.33	3
86	4	31	30	7.75	7.50	5
97	2	10	12	5.00	6.00	3
125	3	23	11	7.67	3.67	2
Total	21	145	138	6.90	6.57	-

Turkish Free-Style National Wrestling Team performed 21 matches and exposed to 145 techniques and gave 138 points (Table 7).

4. Discussion and Conclusion

85 wrestlers from 19 different countries participated the International Senior 12th World Universities Wrestling Championship Freestyle and 76 matches were analyzed. International Senior 12th World Universities Wrestling Championship Freestyle Ranking, Turkey was ranked 3 at the end of the Championship (Table 6).

Atan and İmamoğlu (2005) 35th World Free-Style Championship, most of the free-style matches finished in official time and by points in all weight categories. In the free style wrestling, were taken total 2376 points, therefore mean of total points was 7.64 preach. İmamoğlu et al, (2008) in a study, most of the competitions finished with points (%80). It was seen that 1803 points were taken in 259 competitions and each wrestler took 6.96 points in a single competition (7.04 for eliminations and 6.60 points for finals). Türkmen et al (2013) was found 2013 Universiade Games in men's Greco-Roman and freestyle wrestling, in the number and victory are as 45.5% and technical victory is as 42.5% with 7 points difference. The total points obtained by the victors in Freestyle for

each match was 7.44. In this study, the number of technical points taken for all weight groups in wrestling competitions was 789 points. The highest number of points was achieved in middleweight groups with 352 and with the maximum number of matches was made with 33 in the middleweight group. In the free style wrestling, ratio for one competition (ROC) was of received number of 10.38 points.

In Soyguden and İmamoglu (2017) study; was a significant difference between the technical and score points according to weight groups. Technical of Lightweight and Middleweight groups is higher from Heavyweight group ($p<0.001$). Points of Lightweight group is higher from Middleweight group ($p<0.05$). In this study, ratio of received points for one competition between Weight Groups found differences ($p<0.05$).

In Soyguden and İmamoglu study (2017); was a significant difference between the technical and score points according to weight groups. Number of technical for one competition between Weight Groups found differences ($p<0.001$). Technical of Lightweight and Middleweight groups is higher from Heavyweight group. Ratio of received points for one competition between Weight Groups found differences ($p<0.05$). Points of Lightweight group are higher from Middleweight group. In this study, the points of Middleweight group are higher from Lightweight and Heavyweight groups. There are differences in the categories that are scored in two studies. It may be due to the characteristics of the wrestlers in these styles.

In Soyguden and İmamoglu study (2017), lightweight wrestlers 79% won by score, while 21% won by technical superiority. In these weight groups, there is no winner by pin. Middleweight wrestlers 81% won by score, while 15.5% won by the technical superiority and 3% won by the pin. Heavyweight wrestlers 83% won by the score, while 11% won by the pin and 5.5% have won by with the technical superiority. In this study, Lightweight wrestlers 51.85% won by score and while 48.15% won by technical superiority. Middleweight wrestlers 48.48% won by score and while 51.52% won by technical superiority. Heavyweight wrestlers 75% won by score and while 25% won by technical superiority. There are differences in the way of winning two style wrestling according to the shapes of matches.

Iran, Russia and Turkey have participated in all category competitions. To get degrees, countries must matches at all sizes. Number of Touch in Heavyweight wrestlers was more than from lightweight and middleweight wrestlers. Coaches in Countries must follow the wrestlers of competing countries. If necessary, it should go to the weight category setting. Some wrestlers recommended wrestled at the top category or bottom category.

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